

LEGAL JOURNALISM: INFLUENCE ON THE FORMATION OF LEGAL AWARENESS OF CITIZENS

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Abstract: The media are the main instrument of public control over the activities of the legislative, the executive and judicial branches of government. At the same time, the judicial and legal reform being carried out in the country she herself needs information support and support from the press. By its nature, it is designed to express and shape public opinion, thereby influencing the legal awareness and legal culture of citizens. This means that the media and journalism act as a factor of sustainable legal education and human rights education, serve as an ideological tool for building a state governed by the rule of law.

Key words: journalism, mass media, legal journalism, law, legal awareness
The legal life of the society is widely covered in the mass media. As a socio-philosophical concept, "the legal life of society" reflects not only the legal reality (phenomena and processes occurring in the legal sphere), but also the behavior of people in the sphere of law, the attitude of a person to law. The mass media cover legal life precisely from the point of view of the individual, which is why crimes and incidents are criminal or, as a rule, criminal. Sometimes they say that anti-criminal issues are an integral part of the content of not only mass, but also high – quality publications. Legal pathology is also a component of legal life, which consists of a set of elements of both positive and negative orientation. By telling the audience about new laws, incidents, investigations of criminal cases, court disputes, etc., journalists form the legal awareness of citizens – the most important element of legal consciousness. The level of development of mass legal awareness directly depends on the extent to which the country's population is legally informed, what is its emotional attitude to the law, and what is the attitude of citizens to comply with legal regulations. It can be said that journalism participates in the development of mass legal awareness on two levels: on the rational level – increasing the legal awareness of the audience, and on the emotional level- forming legal values and guidelines, a positive attitude to the law, helping to overcome legal nihilism, and the transition of legal knowledge into beliefs.

Of course, there are other channels of legal information, or, in other words, legal education of the population. These include Legal Information Centers attached to public libraries, computer-based legal information systems, and specialized legal publications – all of which disseminate legal information expressed in the norms of law. Obtaining this information requires quite serious efforts on the part of an untrained (i.e., not having a legal education) consumer.

Educational institutions and specialized legal institutions (for example, the prosecutor's office and the bar) are also able to convey information about the norms of law only to a limited number of people or to a limited extent. And only the mass media constantly, systematically and popularly provide the mass audience with information about the facts, events and phenomena of the legal life of society. Unlike other channels for the dissemination of legal information, mass media do not disseminate the norms of law, but stories related to the law and law enforcement tokens that contain a description of specific legal situations involving people. Thus, the legal life of society is an object of legal journalism – the same subject-thematic specialization of media employees, such as, for example, business-independent journalism, political, sports, or environmental journalism.

In legal journalism, there are different and very different directions: legal (specialized printed publications for lawyers, scientific and professional), criminal (operational reports in the media about crimes, coverage and analysis of law enforcement agencies), judicial (publications and broadcasts about courts, judges and court cases), advisory (answers to questions). answer questions from readers and listeners). The authors' goals correspond to the intentions of publications, categories, and programs. For example, the criminal direction of legal journalism is typical for mass media that aim to give the audience the maximum amount of information about the surrounding reality, and sometimes even shock them with this information. This trend is also present in high-quality publications that not only report on criminal facts, but also analyze them, evaluate and comment on the activities of law enforcement agencies.

If specialized legal publications are aimed more at forming a scientific (theoretical) or professional legal consciousness of a social group of lawyers, then under the influence of legal information in the socio-political media, it is the mass (empirical or ordinary) legal consciousness that is formed. Specific legal situations displayed in the "broad media" turn into objects of cognition and are recognized as causes of experience, i.e. they affect the psyche (and then the

behavior and behavior of the individual).- people - and this allows the media audience to learn complex legal concepts without much effort. Exciting, psychological texts and plots with elements of detective stories often have a stronger impact on the formation of legal awareness of readers and viewers than texts of laws, discussions or opinions of legal experts. At the same time, journalism can affect the mass legal consciousness not only constructively, but also in a dysfunctional way. It is destructive, for example, in cases when journalists show unprofessionalism and legal incompetence, legal nihilism, when the criminal world is romanticized in the mass media and criminal morality is replicated.

The strength and focus of the psychological impact of court stories on the legal awareness of the media audience is determined by the professionalism of court reporters and columnists. Judicial journalism is a special journalistic specialization that gives journalists the opportunity to control the judicial power on behalf of society, to advocate for the restoration of violated rights, and for justice. At the same time, journalists solve pragmatic, mercantile tasks, because the court stories that reveal the most important facts of the case are often used by the public personal, sometimes unexpected manifestations of human nature always attract the attention of the audience and contribute to the popularity of the publication and the author. At the same time, court reporters and observers need to have an understanding of the judicial system and its information policy, the specifics of sources and access to judicial information, the ethics of interaction with courts, the rules for filming and broadcasting in courtrooms, etc.

Regional and local media also cover cases of serious criminal offenses, but less often-trials in cases related to well-known people in the region. Civil disputes are covered mainly in cases where decisions concern everyone, for example, disputes about housing and utilities tariffs, benefits, loans, etc. Appear in the regional press and publications about how the court reinstated an illegally dismissed person, protected someone's right to inheritance, etc. However, the main topics of court publications are: mass, regional and local publications are social and everyday crimes and offenses committed on the basis of relationships between people: murder, theft, robbery, fraud.